

C-27, C-29 and C-30 of the former are shifted upfield by 6.3, 5.3, 6.5, 3.3, 2.7, 9.9 and 2.4 ppm respectively compared to those of the corresponding carbon atoms of the latter. On the other hand C-12, C-16, C-17, C-18, C-20 and C-22 of the former compound appear at lowerfields by 2.7, 1.0, 0.8, 11.8, 8.3 and 4.2 ppm respectively, than the corresponding carbon atoms of erythrodiol diacetate. Such differences of the δ_c values have already been shown^{8,4,5} to be diagnostic of isomeric pairs of ursane and oleanane derivatives and the above results provide further corroboration of the above generalisation.

Experimental

Air dried powdered aerial parts of *V. cotinifolium* (1 Kg) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. Concentration of the petrol extract deposited a white solid which was filtered. The solid and the filtrate were separately chromatographed over silica gel (60-100 mesh). Evaporation of the petrol-EtOAc (10 : 1) eluate from each chromatogram gave uvaol (total yield 0.04%), crystallised from methanol, m. p. 215°. ν_{\max}^{KBr} 3420 cm^{-1} (OH); ^1H nmr: δ_{ppm} 5.2, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C}$); 3.36,

2H, AB_q ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{OH}$); 3.28, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}-\text{OH}$) and 0.8-1.1, 21H (7 C-methyls); MS: significant peaks at m/e (relative abundance) 442(4.1), 411(3.6), 235(4.2), 234(22.3), 217(2.5), 216(6.6), 208(3.0), 207(15.7), 205(3.1), 204(17.3), 203(100), 191(3.0), 190(3.7), 189(6.6), 187(3.4), 177(3.3), 176(3.5), 175(3.5), 161(3.1), 147(4.9), 145(4.6), 135(5.8), 134(4.1), 133(23.2) and 119(11.3). Diacetyl uvaol: ν_{\max} 1735 and 1245 cm^{-1} (OAc); ^1H nmr: δ_{ppm} 5.16, 1H, m ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{C}$); 3.83, 2H, AB_q ($-\text{CH}_2\text{OAc}$); 4.53, 1H, m ($-\text{CHOAc}$); 2.03, 6H, s ($-\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{Me}$);

0.86-1.23, 21H (7 C-methyls). ^{13}C nmr of uvaol diacetate: $^*\delta_{\text{ppm}}$ 38.3(C-1), 23.1(C-2), 80.4(C-3), 37.4(C-4), 55.0(C-5), 18.0(C-6), 32.5(C-7), 39.7(C-8), 47.4(C-9), 36.6(C-10), 17.1(C-11), 125.2(C-12), 138(C-13), 42(C-14), 26(C-15), 23.1(C-16), 36.5(C-17), 54.2(C-18), 39.6(C-19), 39.0(C-20), 30.6(C-21), 35.5(C-22), 27.8(C-23), 16.5(C-24), 15.5(C-25), 16.5(C-26), 23.1(C-27), 70.7(C-28), 23.1(C-29), 21.0(C-30),

170.3($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 20.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 170.1($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 21.0($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$). ^{13}C nmr of erythrodiol diacetate: $^*\delta_{\text{ppm}}$ 38.2(C-1), 23.4(C-2), 80.7(C-3), 37.6(C-4), 55.1(C-5), 18.1(C-6), 32.4(C-7), 39.6(C-8), 47.4(C-9), 36.7(C-10), 23.4(C-11), 122.5(C-12), 143.3(C-13), 41.5(C-14), 25.5(C-15), 22.1(C-16), 35.7(C-17),

42.4(C-18), 46.1(C-19), 30.7(C-20), 33.9(C-21), 31.3(C-22), 27.9(C-23), 16.6(C-24), 15.5(C-25), 16.6(C-26), 25.8(C-27), 70.5(C-28), 33.0(C-29), 23.4(C-30), 170.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 20.8($-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 170.5($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), 21.1($-\text{O}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$). [$^*\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$].

Further elution of the chromatograms with petrol-EtOAc (5 : 1) afforded ursolic acid, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m. p. 285° (total yield 0.25%). The chloroform and the methanol extracts gave only traces of the above compounds.

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Chemical Examination of the Leaves and Stem Heartwood of *Tebebuia pentaphylla* (Linn) Hemsl (Bignoniaceae)

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TEBEBUIA pentaphylla (Linn) Hemsl [Syn. *Tecoma pentaphylla* Juss, *Pink tecomasalvador*, *Pink trumpet*, *Bignonia pentaphylla* (Linn)¹] is a medium sized tree, native to tropical America. It is planted in lawns and squares for flowers which appear on leafless shoots. The wood is light yellow to grey-brown, very hard and bears a superficial resemblance to oak. It is moderately light to fairly heavy, medium to coarse textured.

The bark is credited with diuretic, antipyretic and alexertic properties. The fruit is also useful as diuretic and the fruit-peel as hypnotic agent¹. Lapachol has been reported as an anti-tumour compound² and has also been recently used as an one-colour acid-base indicator³. Hentriacontanol^{4,5} is reported to be insecticide, fungicide and is also physiologically active. Literature reveals that no work, however, has been reported on any part of *T. pentaphylla* though studies on relation between heartwood fibre and its pulp sheet properties have been reported by Tamolang *et al*⁶.

The present note deals with the examination of the leaves and the stem heartwood of this tree. Both, leaves and stem heartwood were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°) and chromatographed over silica gel separately. Elution of the columns with the solvents of increasing polarity afforded the following compounds.

Leaves :

1. *Hentriacontanol-1* : Petroleum ether eluate, m.p. 84°, acetate (Ac₂O/pyridine), m. p. 69° and comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen* confirmed its identity as hentriacontanol.

2. *Hentriacontane* : Petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 64°, M⁺(436) confirmed its identity as hentriacontane.

3. *Dehydrotectol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate, m.p. 193-94°, its conversion into tectol and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic specimen confirmed its identity as dehydrotectol.

4. *Lapachol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) eluate, m.p. 139-40°, positive towards colour test for quinonoid compounds having chelated hydroxy group⁷. Its conversion into β -lapachone and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample confirmed its identity as lapachol.

5. β -*Sitosterol* : Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 136-37°, positive to Liebermann-Burchard test⁸, acetate m.p. 126°, benzoate m.p. 143-43° and comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen confirmed its identity.

Stem Heartwood :

1. *Nonacosane* : Petroleum ether eluate, m.p. 62°, M⁺(408), was identified as nonacosane.

2. *Dehydro-tectol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 3) eluate, m.p. 193-94°, confirmed by direct comparison (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic specimen.

3. *Lapachol* : Petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate, m.p. 139-40°, identical (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample of lapachol.

* Some obtained from Prof. K. C. Joshi of the University of Rajasthan, Jaipur and some isolated by the authors themselves (*Die Pharmazie*, 1980, 35, 122).

4. β -*Sitosterol* : Benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) eluate, m.p. 136-37°, identical (m. m. p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample of β -sitosterol.

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Chemical Constituents of *Atalantia monophylla* (Correa)

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ATALANTIA monophylla Correa (Fam. Rutaceae), a medicinal plant¹ collected from Orissa, has been shown to contain acridone alkaloids², limonoids³⁻⁴ and several other compounds⁵. Further investigation of the petroleum ether extract of the leaves and benzene extract of the heartwood led to the isolation of *n*-butyl palmitate and β -sitosterol (leaves) and palmitic, stearic and arachidic acids (heartwood).

Finely ground dried leaves of *Atalantia monophylla* (6.2 Kg) were extracted with cold petroleum ether (60-80°) for 25 days. The concentrated extract (58 g) was chromatographed over silica gel to furnish an ester fraction, which on rechromatography gave *n*-butyl palmitate (I) C₂₀H₄₀O₂ (1.18 g) as a yellowish liquid; b.p. 165-170°/10 mm; ir: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{NaCl}}$ 1375 cm⁻¹ (>C=O, ester); MS: m/e 312 (M⁺).

Alkaline hydrolysis of I gave palmitic acid identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Conversion of palmitic acid into its *n*-butyl ester gave a compound which had the same retention time as I on glc.

The identity of β -sitosterol m.p. 137-39°, was established by direct comparison with an authentic sample.